

More than just infrastructure: How collaboration is essential to building an open research data repository community in Canada

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Overview

- Early currents of Dataverse in Canada
- Establishing a national Dataverse repository
- Collaborating to build an inclusive national Dataverse community
- Discussion

Early currents of Dataverse in Canada

What is Dataverse?

- Open-source repository platform to deposit, publish, share, and discover research data
- Developed and maintained since 2006 by the Institute of Quantitative Social Science (IQSS) at Harvard University
- 78 installations around the world
- Developed with quantitative social science data in mind, but not limited to any domain
- Support for the FAIR data principles

<https://dataverse.org/>

Emerging Dataverse installations in Canada

- Academic libraries recognizing need for research data repositories to support data deposit, sharing and discovery
- Institutions across Canada began hosting installations of the Dataverse software in 2010s
- Developed expertise and recognized need to share knowledge

Dataverse North Working Group (2017)

- Formed by stakeholders at institutions across Canada.
- Part of the Portage "Network of Experts."
 - Portage: an RDM organization sponsored by the Canadian Association of Research Libraries.
- Mandate:
 - "Develop a community of practice for libraries using or interested in using the Dataverse repository platform for research data in Canada."
- Sub-working groups:
 - Business models
 - Metadata
 - Training

Year 1 Recommendations (2018)

- Business models group:
 - Survey of Canadian institutions using or hosting Dataverse to gauge capacity for supporting Dataverse service.
 - Environmental scan of repository service models.
- Key recommendation:
 - Establish a national Dataverse service hosted by Scholars Portal at University of Toronto Libraries.
- Benefits:
 - Realize economies of scale.
 - Enable equitable access for institutions across Canada.
 - Leverage existing expertise and infrastructure.

Portage Network

**Dataverse North Working Group:
Year 1 Recommendations**

Prepared by:
Portage Dataverse North Working Group (DVNWG)

March 2018

Dataverse North Outputs

- Metadata best practices guide (2019-2021) [\[link\]](#)
- "Introduction to Dataverse" training module (2021) [\[link\]](#)
- Templates for creating local Dataverse policies (2021) [\[link\]](#)

Dataverse North Metadata Best Practices Guide

Version 3.0
September 2021

By Dataverse North

Prepared by the Portage Network for the New Digital Research

NDRIO

Network of Digital Research Infrastructure Organizations

NOIRN

Network of Open Infrastructure Research Networks

engagedr.ca

Citation Metadata Block

Field	Definition with tips	Usage ²⁷	Repeatable	Example
Title	Full title by which the Dataset is known.	RQ	No	Social Media Use Among Teens, 2015 (Canada)
Subtitle	A secondary title used to amplify or state certain limitations on the main title. <i>Tip: The subtitle is not included in the auto-generated citation. If you want the subtitle to be included in the citation, then you must add it to the Title field in addition to the Subtitle field. The Subtitle field.</i>	O	No	Main Survey
Alternative Title	A title by which the work is commonly referred, or an abbreviation of the title. <i>Tip: Acronym, short form, or translation of full title.</i>	O	No	Youth Social Media Survey
Alternative URL	A URL where the dataset can be viewed, such as a personal or project website.	O	No	https://youthsocialmedia.org
Other ID	Another unique identifier that identifies this Dataset (e.g., producer's or another repository's number).	O	No	
Agency	Name of agency which generated this Identifier.	O	Yes	Youth Communication Development Project, Education Department, Queen's University
Identifier	Other Identifier that corresponds to this Dataset.	O	Yes	2202
Author	The person(s), corporate body(ies), or agency(ies) responsible for creating the work.			
Name	The author's Family Name, Given Name or the name of the organization responsible for this Dataset.	RQ	Yes	Doe, Jane
Affiliation	The organization with which the author is affiliated. <i>Tip: Use the full official name of the organization; avoid abbreviations.</i>	R	Yes	Queen's University
Identifier Scheme	Name of the Identifier scheme (ORCID, ISNI). <i>Note: This field is a drop-down list; select one.</i>	R	Yes	ORCID
Identifier	Uniquely identifies an individual author or organization, according to various schemes.	R	Yes	https://orcid.org/0000-0001-1825-0097
Contact	The contact(s) for this Dataset.			
Name	The contact's Family Name, Given Name or the name of the organization.	R	Yes	Doe, Jane

²⁷ RQ = Required; R = Recommended; O = Optional

Portage Network New Digital Research Infrastructure Organization 8

Establishing a national Dataverse repository

From a regional to national Dataverse service

- Launched in 2012 as a service of the Ontario Council of University Libraries hosted at the University of Toronto Libraries
- Extended service nationally in 2020 in partnership with the 4 the regional academic library consortia in Canada representing 60+ subscribing institutions
- Each institution manages their own collection and supports their local users
- In process of renaming to better reflect new identity as a national service

Initiating community support for Dataverse service

- Institutional contacts group
 - Comprised of administrators from institutions using the Scholars Portal Dataverse (SPDV) service (now 60 institutions)
- Created spaces for exchange of information and feedback
 - Private email list-serv to support end-users and for discussion
 - Monthly meetings
- Recognized need for more formal collaboration with Dataverse North

**Collaborating to build an inclusive
national Dataverse community**

Renewal of Dataverse North (2021)

- Landscape had changed:
 - National Dataverse service had been established.
 - Growing community of Dataverse administrators.
 - Portage absorbed into Digital Research Alliance of Canada.
- Had Dataverse North outlived its purpose?
 - No—The need to advocate for community remained.
 - Designation changed from Working Group to Expert Group.
- Scholars Portal Dataverse Team agreed to collaborate with Dataverse North on community development.
- Alliance RDM Team pledged logistical support.
- Feedback from community was supportive.

Digital Research
Alliance of Canada

Alliance de recherche
numérique du Canada

Network of Experts

The Network of Experts is critical in developing and providing resources, expert advice and practical help to assist with the management of research data at every stage of the data lifecycle. Our experts include librarians, data management professionals, institutional research officers, ethics officers and members of government and non-governmental organizations from across Canada.

Expert and Working Groups are ongoing and responsible for particular stages related to the RDM life cycle. Current Groups include:

Curation Expert Group

Data Management Planning Expert Group

Data Repositories Expert Group

Dataverse North Expert Group

Discovery and Metadata Expert Group

Community Facilitation Team

- Vehicle for communication, coordination, and collaboration.
- Brings together:
 - Scholars Portal Dataverse Team
 - Dataverse North Chair
 - Alliance staff
- Monthly meetings since January 2022.
- Plans the regular bilingual community meetings.
- Coordinates other activities, like training.
- Identifies and arranges needed supports.

Canadian Dataverse Community

Community-building achievements

Creation of community spaces to exchange knowledge and feedback

Development of resources, such as training modules, guides, and templates

Incorporating bilingual community meetings and support

Channeling feedback into the development of software, tools, and resources

Discussion and next steps

Challenges and goals

Broaden community participation by establishing open community meetings and list-serv

Supporting needs of French-speakers at community meetings and in developing resources.

Help to mitigate disparities in support services

Respond to the needs of the community with new activities and initiatives

Conclusion

- Collaboration between the service provider and community groups is essential to cultivate an inclusive and sustainable national community.
- Overall aim of the community – to facilitate the successful sharing and reuse of research data – aligns with national efforts to strengthen digital research infrastructure and the RDM community.
- National networks like this one contribute to the international Dataverse community and provide a model for sustainable community development.

Questions?

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Stay tuned for the Borealis launch on June 23 at borealisdata.ca

References

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